

Benchmarking Nonlinear Readouts in Linear Reservoir Networks

Giacomo Lagomarsini^[0009-0008-2395-8891], Andrea Ceni^[0000-0002-5084-0505],
and Claudio Gallicchio^[0000-0002-6692-2564]

Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa, Largo Bruno Pontecorvo, 3 -
56127, Italy

`g.lagomarsini@studenti.unipi.it`^{**} ,
`{andrea.ceni claudio.gallicchio}@unipi.it`

Abstract. Recent theoretical advances have demonstrated the universality of linear Reservoir Computing (RC) models equipped with nonlinear readouts, showing their potential to approximate arbitrary input-output mappings. However, practical insights into the selection and performance of nonlinear readouts are limited. This paper addresses this gap by systematically benchmarking a spectrum of nonlinear readouts within linear RC frameworks. Our results reveal the practical trade-offs in accuracy and efficiency across tasks, offering insights on how to train performant RC systems with linear recurrence. These findings provide valuable guidelines for designing efficient recurrent architectures that combine theoretical guarantees with state-of-the-art performance in sequential data processing.

Keywords: Reservoir Computing · Echo State Networks · Linearity

1 Introduction

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are fundamental tools for modeling sequential and temporal data, offering powerful capabilities for tasks such as speech processing, time-series prediction, and control systems [6]. However, training RNNs effectively remains a challenge due to issues like vanishing gradients and high computational complexity, particularly when optimizing recurrent connections [10]. To address these challenges, Reservoir Computing (RC) emerged in the years as an alternative training approach for RNNs, where the recurrent dynamics are fixed, and the learning capacity resides in an external readout function [7, 8, 12, 13]. Recently, a growing body of theoretical work has established the universality of linear RC models equipped with nonlinear readouts, demonstrating their ability to approximate arbitrary input-output mappings under certain conditions. These results provide a strong theoretical foundation for the potential of such systems in solving complex computational tasks. However, despite these universality theorems, the choice of nonlinear readout function is

^{**} Corresponding author

far from trivial, as the practical performance of different approaches can vary significantly. Understanding which nonlinear readouts are most effective remains an open question, motivating further empirical investigation.

Parallel to these theoretical advances, recent developments in deep learning have highlighted the practical power of linear recurrent systems, particularly in the context of linear State-Space Models (SSMs). Architectures like Structured State Space Model (S4) [4] and Linear Recurrent Unit (LRU) [9] have demonstrated exceptional performance across sequential learning tasks, achieving state-of-the-art results by leveraging linear recurrence for efficient sequence modeling while relegating nonlinear processing to specialized layers or blocks. These exceptional results suggest that shifting nonlinear operations outside the recurrence dynamics may not only preserve theoretical universality, but also improve computational efficiency and generalization in real-world applications.

Building on these theoretical insights and empirical breakthroughs, this paper investigates the effectiveness of various nonlinear readouts appended to linear RC models. Specifically, we conduct a systematic empirical evaluation of different trainable nonlinear functions, aiming to identify promising approaches that can harness the universal approximation power predicted by theory while achieving robust performance in practice. By bridging the theoretical underpinnings of RC with the experimental progress in deep learning, our work provides critical insights into the design of efficient and expressive models for sequential data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the required fundamental concepts on RC. Section 3 introduces the concept of linear reservoirs with nonlinear readouts, exploring their theoretical foundations and practical implementations. Section 4 presents our experimental analysis. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of our findings and potential avenues for future research.

2 Reservoir Computing

RC is a computational framework for efficiently training RNNs to process sequential and time-series data. The key idea of RC is to leverage the high-dimensional dynamics of a randomly initialised, fixed recurrent layer, called the reservoir, and train only a lightweight dense layer, called the readout.

The Echo State Network (ESN) model is the most prominent form of reservoir computer. This model consists of a nonlinear reservoir function, that defines the state dynamic of the model, $\mathbf{h}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b})$, where $\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ is the input vector at time t , $\mathbf{h}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h}$ is the state space vector at time t , $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h \times N_h}$, and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h \times N_x}$ are the hidden-to-hidden and input-to-hidden reservoir matrices, and \mathbf{b} is the bias. The components of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are randomly drawn. We call \mathbf{A} the *reservoir matrix*, and \mathbf{B} the *input matrix* of the ESN. The readout function is simply a linear transformation, trained using least-squares regression. Usually, the ESN also comprises a leakage term, making the state equation

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \alpha \tanh(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}) + (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is the leak rate. A reservoir computer with state transition function (1) is called a Leaky ESN.

A foundational concept in the theory of RC is the Echo State Property (ESP), which ensures the ability of the RC to process and store information in a stable and reliable manner. The ESP requires that the influence of initial conditions on the reservoir state vanishes over time, allowing the reservoir dynamics to develop a high-dimensional representation uniquely determined by the input signal driving the dynamics [14]. Precisely, we refer to the following definition of the ESP.

Definition 1. *Let $F(\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{x})$ be a function from $\mathbb{R}^{N_h} \times \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ to \mathbb{R}^{N_h} . We say that F satisfies the Echo State Property (ESP) if, given any sequence $(\mathbf{x}_i)_i$, and any pair of initial conditions $\mathbf{h}_0, \mathbf{h}'_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h}$, then*

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{h}_t - \mathbf{h}'_t\| = 0, \quad (2)$$

where, for each $t \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathbf{h}_t = F(\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, \mathbf{x}_t)$ and $\mathbf{h}'_t = F(\mathbf{h}'_{t-1}, \mathbf{x}_t)$

A simple sufficient condition assuring the ESP for ESN models is $\|\mathbf{A}\| < 1$, where $\|\mathbf{A}\|$ denotes the spectral norm of the reservoir matrix \mathbf{A} . However, this condition constraints the reservoir dynamics to be strictly contracting at each time step. A widespread rule of thumb is to set the spectral radius $\rho(\mathbf{A})$ to be around 1. This results in a necessary condition for the ESP for the particular case of zero input.

3 Linear Reservoirs with nonlinear Readout

Classically ESNs are provided with a nonlinear reservoir and a linear readout. Here we move the nonlinearity at the readout level keeping the reservoir dynamics linear. Specifically, we define a (leaky) Linear Reservoir Network (LRN) as the RC model with state-update function

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \alpha(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}) + (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, \quad (3)$$

and readout function $\mathbf{y}_t = f(\mathbf{h}_t)$, where f is a nonlinear function. Because the reservoir is linear, f should be nonlinear, or else the system should be able to only approximate linear systems. Our objective is validating possible readout functions, and finding the best trade-off between expressivity and computational complexity. Moreover, we want to verify if the linear reservoir is, in practice, expressive enough, when compared with a nonlinear leaky ESN. In the remainder of this section, in 3.1, we briefly recall results on expressivity of linear reservoirs, and draw parallelism to linear reservoir models, in particular State Space Models (SSMs). Next, in 3.2 we analyze the ESP of LRN, providing sufficient and necessary conditions. Finally, we introduce a range of possible readout functions, discussing theoretical expressivity and complexity.

3.1 Related Work

Universality of Linear Reservoirs. Expressivity of linear reservoir has been studied in various settings. Grygoreva et al. [3] states that linear reservoir with universal readout are universal in the class of time-invariant, fading memory filter with deterministic inputs, i.e. they can approximate arbitrarily well any filter in such class. This expressivity result is the very same proved for ESNs in [2]. For both ESN and linear reservoirs, the results have also been extended for stochastic inputs [1] (Proposition III.1).

State Space Models. Linear recurrence has been popularized in the context of deep learning as a possible alternative to classic RNN processing by structured SSMS like S4 [4] and LRU [9]. These innovative recurrent architectures are designed to maximize the memory capacity of the network, by dropping the nonlinearity between the recurrence steps, and smart initialization of the recurrence matrix. In SSMS, the dynamic of the hidden state $\mathbf{h}(t)$ is viewed as a continuous time dynamical system that is then integrated in a discrete time model. Then, SSMS focused on trying to find recurrence matrices that guarantee both efficiency in the matrix-vector multiplication, and long memory. Linear Recurrent Unit (LRU) showed that it is not necessary to view the dynamic as a discrete version of a continuous time system. They instead focused on initializing the transition matrix diagonally. The initialization allows to directly control the eigenvalues of the reservoir matrix. This approach is closer to that used in initializing the matrix in ESN theory, where the main concern is controlling the dynamic of the state transition function. The approach of LRU, though, moves the dynamic in the complex field. Instead, in this work we use a dense real matrix.

3.2 ESP of Linear Reservoirs

For LRNs, the ESP can be investigated through an exact analysis, due to the lack of the nonlinearity in the recurrence.

Theorem 1. *An LRN of Equation (3) satisfies the ESP (2) if and only if $\rho(\alpha\mathbf{A} + (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{I}) < 1$.*

Proof. The effective transition matrix of Equation (3) is $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \alpha\mathbf{A} + (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{I}$. Consider any vector $\mathbf{h}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h}$. Let \mathbf{h}_{t+1} be the state vector obtained at time $t + 1$ from the initial condition \mathbf{h}_0 . Since the recursion is linear, we can unroll it to make the dependency of \mathbf{h}_{t+1} from \mathbf{h}_0 explicit:

$$\mathbf{h}_{t+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{h}_t + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_{t+1} \quad (4)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^2\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_{t+1} \quad (5)$$

$$= \underbrace{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{t+1}\mathbf{h}_0}_{i.c. \text{ dependence}} + \sum_{i=0}^t \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^i \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_{t-i} \quad (6)$$

If $\rho(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) < 1$ then $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{t+1}$ converges to null matrix, as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Since $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{t+1}\mathbf{h}_0$ is the only dependence on the initial state, the ESP holds. This proves the sufficient condition for the ESP.

Otherwise, if $\rho(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) > 1$, take \mathbf{h}_0 as the eigenvector associated to an eigenvalue λ of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, such that $|\lambda| > 1$, and $\mathbf{h}'_0 = \mathbf{0}$. Then, from (4)-(6), $\|\mathbf{h}_{t+1} - \mathbf{h}'_{t+1}\|_2 = \|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{t+1}\mathbf{h}_0\|_2 = |\lambda|^{t+1} \cdot \|\mathbf{h}_0\|$ diverges. Therefore, if $\rho(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) > 1$, the ESP does not hold. This proves the necessary condition.

We can see from Equation (6) that the term involving the initial condition vanishes with the power of the reservoir matrix, if and only if the spectral radius $\rho(\mathbf{A}) < 1$. Therefore, the rule of thumb used in traditional ESNs turns out a necessary and sufficient condition for the ESP in an LRN model. Moreover, a sufficient condition for the ESP holds for LRN similar to standard nonlinear ESNs, as stated in the proposition below.

Proposition 1. *Let us call $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \alpha\mathbf{A} + (1-\alpha)\mathbf{I}$. An LRN of Equation (3) satisfies the ESP (2) if $\|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\|_2 < 1$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{h}_0, \mathbf{h}'_0$ be two vectors in \mathbb{R}^{N_h} , and $(\mathbf{x}_i)_i$ be any sequence of inputs. By hypothesis, $\|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\|_2 < 1$, therefore there exists an $\epsilon > 0$ such that $\|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\|_2 = (1-\epsilon) < 1$. Then, for any $t \in \mathbb{N}$, by a recursive argument we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{h}_t - \mathbf{h}'_t\|_2 &= \|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_t - (\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{h}'_{t-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_t)\|_2 \\ &= \|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{h}_{t-1} - \mathbf{h}'_{t-1})\|_2 \\ &\leq \|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\|_2 \cdot \|\mathbf{h}_{t-1} - \mathbf{h}'_{t-1}\|_2 \\ &= (1-\epsilon) \cdot \|\mathbf{h}_{t-1} - \mathbf{h}'_{t-1}\|_2 \leq \dots \\ &\leq (1-\epsilon)^t \cdot \|\mathbf{h}_0 - \mathbf{h}'_0\| \xrightarrow{t \rightarrow \infty} 0. \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, the sufficient condition for the ESP of Proposition 1 is much stronger than Theorem 1, since the former implies contraction at each time step, while the latter is an asymptotic condition of stability.

3.3 Nonlinear readout functions

In traditional ESNs, the system exhibits nonlinearity in its recurrent dynamics, while the readout layer is typically a simple linear model, often trained in closed form. When using a linear reservoir model, a nonlinearity must necessarily be in the readout, otherwise we lose guarantees of universality. There are several choices for this nonlinearity, and now we will analyze those that we will benchmark in the next section.

tanh Readout The most straightforward option is moving the tanh nonlinearity after the recursion, obtaining a readout of the form

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{W}\tanh(\mathbf{h}_t), \tag{7}$$

where \mathbf{W} is the trainable readout matrix. We call this readout function a tanh readout.

Fig. 1. Left: LRN reservoir; the only distinction from a standard ESN is the absence of a nonlinear transformation after combining the input and recurrent components, represented by a $+$ symbol. **Right:** possible readout functions considered: any nonlinearity followed by a linear layer, an MLP, and a GLU-MLP. Notice that in the case given by *nonlinearity+Linear Readout*, in the paper we consider as σ nonlinearity either the hyperbolic tangent \tanh or a degree 2 polynomial. See details in the text (Section 3.3).

Polynomial Readout Linear reservoir computers with polynomial readouts

$$\mathbf{y}_t = p(\mathbf{h}_t) \quad (8)$$

have been shown to be universal approximators of fading memory filters in [3]. This readout can simply be trained by creating the polynomial features and fitting the coefficients of the polynomial. For example, suppose we are training a polynomial readout p of degree 2, and denote by $(\mathbf{h}_t)_i$ the i -th component of the vector \mathbf{h}_t . In this case,

$$p(\mathbf{h}_t) = \sum_{i,j=0, i \geq j}^{N_h} p_{i,j}^{(2)} \cdot (\mathbf{h}_t)_i \cdot (\mathbf{h}_t)_j + \sum_{k=0}^{N_h} p_k^{(1)} \cdot (\mathbf{h}_t)_k + p^{(0)},$$

where $p_{i,j}^{(2)}$ are the polynomial coefficients relative to the degree 2 part, $p_i^{(1)}$ are the coefficient relative to the linear part, and $p^{(0)}$ is the constant. Concretely, first we create the polynomial variables, multiplying $(\mathbf{h}_t)_i \cdot (\mathbf{h}_t)_j$ for each pair of reservoir variables i and j . Calling \mathbf{z}_t the vector obtained by concatenating the second degree and the first degree variables, we can train the readout using least square regression on $\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_t$. Notice that, in general, the dimensionality of \mathbf{z}_t will be much larger than \mathbf{h}_t . As a result, despite the polynomial readout being also trainable in closed form, the training could be more expensive than that of a \tanh readout.

MLP Readout Another possible class of readouts is that of one hidden layer MLP readouts,

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{W}_1 \sigma(\mathbf{W}_2 \mathbf{h}_t) = \text{MLP}(\mathbf{h}_t), \quad (9)$$

where σ is a nonlinearity.

MLP readouts are a family of functions that approximate arbitrarily well any continuous function in a compact space, therefore as shown in [1] (Corollary III.6), the resulting reservoir model is universal.

GLU-MLP Readout In many state space models [4, 9, 11], a Gated Linear Unit (GLU) is used between each recurrence layer and before the feed-forward readout. A GLU layer is defined by

$$\mathbf{z}_t = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{h}_t * \sigma(\mathbf{W}_g\mathbf{h}_t), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{W}_g \in \mathbb{R}^{N_z \times N_h}$ are trainable matrices, σ is the sigmoid function, and $*$ is a component-wise product. Therefore, we also benchmarked a GLU-MLP readout, that is composed by a GLU layer and one hidden layer MLP.

Figure 1 illustrates the LRN model, with the benchmarked nonlinear readouts. Table 1 shows the number of trainable parameters for each readout type, assuming the same reservoir size N_h and number of outputs N_y . For MLP-based models, we tied the size of the hidden layer to the reservoir size. Moreover, we only reported the leading coefficients (e.g. we omitted the biases from the count).

Table 1. Number of trainable parameters for each readout type, in function of the reservoir size N_h , and the output size N_y .

readout	trainable parameters	trainable in closed form
tanh	$N_h \cdot N_y$	Yes
poly (degree p)	$\frac{(N_h+p) \cdots (N_h+1)}{p!} \cdot N_y$	Yes
MLP	$N_h^2 + N_h \cdot N_y$	No
GLU-MLP	$3N_h^2 + N_h \cdot N_y$	No

4 Experiments

In this section, we present a comparative analysis of the different readouts introduced in Section 3. Section 4.1 lists the explored variants for the experimental analysis, as well as the model selection for each model. In Section 4.2, we describe the tasks used for benchmarking the different models. Finally, Section 4.3 presents the results and a discussion of the model performances.

4.1 Experimental Setting

Variants Explored. We study the performance of the different readouts on various tasks concerning time-series regression and sequence classification. For sequence classification tasks, we use the last states produced from each sequence as inputs to the readout. The readout we have chosen to consider following Section 3.3 are:

- A tanh readout, followed by a linear matrix, trained using ridge regression, labeled *LRN-tanh*
- a polynomial readout, also trained using ridge regression, labeled *LRN-poly*. We fixed the degree of the polynomial to 2.
- a one-hidden-layer MLP readout, labeled *LRN-MLP*.
- a GLU layer, followed by a one-hidden-layer MLP readout, labeled *LRN-GLU*.

Regarding the MLPs of the last two readouts, we simplified the setup and improved training efficiency by setting the hidden size equal to the reservoir size of the models. We also report, as baselines, the results of a standard leaky ESN and a linear reservoir with linear readout, trained through ridge regression, labeled LRN-linear.

Model Selection. For the time series regression tasks (NARMA and MG), the models selection was performed using grid-search for LRN-tanh and LRN-poly. We instead performed a Bayesian Search for LRN-MLP and LRN-GLU, due to the larger number of hyper-parameters, and the more computationally expensive training. The search was stopped after 300 configurations. For the classification tasks (sMNIST and psMNIST), we performed a Bayesian Search for all the models, stopped after 300 configurations. For time-series regression tasks, the normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE) is used as the evaluation metric. It is calculated by dividing the root mean squared error by the root mean square of the target values, ensuring normalization. For classification tasks, we measured the accuracy score. For all models and tasks, we explored key hyperparameters of the Echo State Network (ESN), including the spectral radius, bias and input matrix scaling, and the leak rate. For the neural network readouts, we used Adam optimizer, and investigated a range of values for learning rate, batch size and weight decay. Table 2 shows the search ranges in detail. In LRN, we constrain the spectral radius ρ to be at most 1 in order to prevent the states from exploding.

4.2 Tasks

We now describe the tasks considered, with the train-validation-test splits. For the time series regression tasks (NARMA and MG) in the training phase we discarded the first 100 steps as warm-up. For the classification task (MNIST), we used the last hidden state for each example to train the readouts.

NARMA. We tested the models on the Nonlinear Autoregressive Moving Average (NARMA) task. The task consists in predicting the state at time t of the time-series $y(t) = 0.3y(t-1) + 0.05y(t-1) \sum_{i=1}^k y(t-i) + 1.5x(t-k)x(t-1) + 0.1$, where $x(t)$ is randomly drawn in $[0, 0.5]$ for each t , and k is a positive whole number, that is the order of the task. We tested the orders $k = 10$ (NARMA10) and $k = 30$ (NARMA30). The first 4000 steps of the time series are used to train the models, then 1000 steps are used for validating, and the last 5000 steps for

testing the model.

Mackey-Glass. Mackey-Glass dynamical system is defined by the differential equation $\frac{df(t)}{dt} = \frac{0.2f(t-17)}{1+f(t-17)^{10}} - 0.1f(t)$. The task is predicting n -steps ahead a numerical integration of the equation, i.e. the target at time t is $y(t) = x(t+n)$. We considered next step prediction, i.e. $n = 1$ (MG) , and also $n = 84$ (84-MG), as in [5], for a more challenging task, that requires considering long-range interactions. The entire time series has a length of 10000 steps, with the first 5000 used for training, the following 1000 for validation, and the last 4000 for testing.

Pixel-by-pixel Image Classification. We also tested the models in two tasks of time series classifications, specifically focusing on pixel-by-pixel image classification. The MNIST datasets consists in gray-scale images of handwritten digits. The resolution of each image is 28×28 pixels. Sequential-MNIST (sMNIST) task consists in predicting the digits of the MNIST dataset, fed pixel-by-pixel to the models. Permuted sequential-MNIST (psMNIST) is a variant of sMNIST, in which a random permutation is applied to the pixels of the images. To perform validation, we split the provided training set of 60000 examples in 48000 for training, and 12000 for validation.

4.3 Results

Table 3 shows the results of the various models in both the regression and classification tasks.

For regression tasks, we used the same reservoir size of 100 for all the models. We notice that the simplest LRN-tanh achieves surprisingly robust results across the majority of the tasks. In particular, LRN-tanh outperforms or does as well as the leaky ESN on 3 out of 4 of the regression tasks, and it is close in the 84-MG. We emphasize once again that this model is the only one with a parameter count comparable to that of the leaky ESN, when the reservoir sizes are equal. We also notice how the addition of a GLU layer enhances the performance of the MLP readout in 3 out of 4 tasks, and obtained the overall best result in 84-MG.

For the case of classification tasks, i.e. sMNIST and psMNIST, we used reservoirs of 500 units. For the polynomial readout (poly), we were not able to perform the training, since it required storing a large number of vectors of more than 250000 units each, after applying the polynomial to the reservoir states. Overall,

Fig. 2. Average ranking of the models (the lower the better), for equal reservoir sizes.

LRN-GLU was the best performing model on the pixel-by-pixel classification, and all LRN models did better or equally well as the Leaky ESN.

We determined an overall best score by ranking models in each task, assigning 1 point to the best-performing model, 2 points to the second-best, and so on. The final average rank was then computed by summing these ranks across all tasks and dividing by the number of tasks. The lower the rank is, the best the model performed. Figure 2 shows the results, highlighting LRN-tanh and LRN-GLU as the two best performing models.

Table 2. Hyperparameters searched. Values of the spectral radius ρ greater than 1 only searched for the ESN.

Reservoir	$\rho \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9, 0.99, 1, 1.1, 2\}$	Values of $\rho > 1$ searched only for Leaky ESN
	$\alpha \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9, 1\}$	
	bias scaling $\in \{0., 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10\}$	
	input scaling $\in \{0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 5\}$	
LRN-tanh and LRN-poly readouts	regularization $\in \{10^{-3}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}, 10^{-7}, 10^{-8}\}$	
LRN-MLP and LRN-GLU readouts	batch size $\in \{64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048\}$ for MNIST, $\{16, 32, 64, 128\}$ for NARMA and MG	
	learning rate $\in \{10^{-2}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}\}$	
	weight decay $\in \{10^{-3}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}, 10^{-7}, 10^{-8}\}$	

Table 3. Results on time-series regression (MG and NARMA) and classification (MNIST) tasks. Number of reservoir units is 100 for regression tasks and 500 for classification tasks. Best model in bold, second best model underlined.

Task	Leaky ESN	LRN-linear	LRN-tanh	LRN-poly	LRN-MLP	LRN-GLU
MG ($\times 10^{-2}$) \downarrow	0.039 \pm 0.005	0.091 \pm 0.0049	0.039 \pm 0.002	<u>0.14 \pm 0.028</u>	0.45 \pm 0.0007	0.43 \pm 0.07
84-MG \downarrow	<u>0.15 \pm 0.03</u>	0.19 \pm 0.02	0.17 \pm 0.03	0.24 \pm 0.02	0.19 \pm 0.08	0.08 \pm 0.02
NARMA10 \downarrow	<u>0.073 \pm 0.006</u>	0.11 \pm 0.00003	0.058 \pm 0.007	0.0063 \pm 0.004	<u>0.023 \pm 0.009</u>	0.037 \pm 0.008
NARMA30 \downarrow	0.19 \pm 0.01	0.20 \pm 0.003	0.12 \pm 0.004	<u>0.15 \pm 0.04</u>	0.19 \pm 0.025	0.17 \pm 0.018
sMNIST \uparrow	76.4 \pm 1.1	63.1 \pm 0.1	<u>77.5 \pm 0.3</u>	–	<u>77.5 \pm 1.7</u>	78.2 \pm 0.3
psMNIST \uparrow	82.3 \pm 3.0	79.6 \pm 0.1	82.3 \pm 3.0	–	<u>86.6 \pm 6.1</u>	88.7 \pm 3.2

Additionally, we analyzed the computational cost of training the models ¹ Table 5 shows the emissions for MG and sMNIST task, for the same reservoir sizes used in the experiments. We can see how LRN-tanh is the only one that has similar emissions and training time to a standard ESN, while all the other models are computationally more expensive. For the sMNIST task, due to the relative large dataset size, the batch size makes a significant difference in training time. The best LRN-MLP model turned out having a smaller batch size than the best LRN-GLU, therefore training LRN-MLP readout resulted to be slower.

We also conducted a comparison of the models by fixing the number of trainable parameters instead of the reservoir size. Specifically, we selected an Echo State Network (ESN) with 1000 reservoir units. Given that the MNIST dataset

¹ Emissions were calculated using CodeCarbon 2.8.2.

Table 4. results on MNIST classification tasks. Number of trainable parameters is approximately 10.000 for every model. Best model in bold, second best model underlined.

Tasks	Leaky ESN	LRN-tanh	LRN-poly	LRN-MLP	LRN-GLU
sMNIST \uparrow	<u>75.5 \pm 1.0</u>	79.1 \pm 1.0	61.8 \pm 1.7	64.8 \pm 3.3	66.8 \pm 1.8
psMNIST \uparrow	<u>83.3 \pm 0.6</u>	85.0 \pm 0.7	73.6 \pm 0.4	72.3 \pm 4.3	52.5 \pm 0.3

Table 5. Emissions and execution time for different readouts, for MG and sMNIST tasks. Reservoir size is respectively 100 and 500. Best model (lower time or emissions) in bold, second best model underlined.

Metric	Leaky ESN	LRN-linear	LRN-tanh	LRN-poly	LRN-MLP	LRN-GLU
MG Emissions (gCO ₂) \downarrow	<u>0.02446</u>	0.02492	0.02341	0.04459	1.21025	3.39883
MG Time (s) \downarrow	<u>0.55</u>	0.56	0.53	0.99	26.98	75.76
sMNIST Emissions (gCO ₂) \downarrow	<u>0.95603</u>	0.95791	0.82342	–	4.49792	3.36130
sMNIST Time (s) \downarrow	<u>20.46</u>	20.51	17.53	–	98.77	73.52

comprises 10 output variables, the total number of trainable parameters amounts to 10000 (excluding the bias term). The LRN-tanh model was configured to have the same number of units, since the number of trainable parameters remains the same. In contrast, the LRN-poly model has only 64 units, while the LRN-MLP and LRN-GLU models have 96 and 57, respectively. The results of the experiment are presented in Table 4. In this case, LRN-tanh performs better than all the other models, and it is the only one achieving better performances than the Leaky ESN. This result highlights the importance of a large and rich reservoir: for the complex readouts, fixing the total number of trainable parameters results in smaller reservoirs for these models, limiting their expressivity.

5 Conclusions

In this work, we have analyzed and benchmarked linear reservoir computers, and investigated the trade-off in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency of various types of readout functions.

Our findings revealed that the simplest LRN-tanh model delivers robust performance, surpassing more complex alternatives in several tasks, while maintaining a computational cost comparable to that of a standard Leaky ESN. Our experiments also indicate that implementing a GLU layer can enhance the performance, but at the cost of a larger number of parameters, and often slower training.

These results reinforce the idea, drawn from SSM literature, that relocating the nonlinearity outside the recurrence can be highly effective in practice, even when applied in the RC domain, and open for further research. One promising direction for future research is the use of structured or diagonal transition matrices, as done in LRU, to enable parallelization of the recurrence. Exploring these structured initializations could lead to models that keep the simplicity and

efficiency of LRNs, while further improving their scalability and applicability to more complex sequential tasks. Overall, this work provides valuable insights into the practical aspect of designing linear reservoir computing models, opening the way for future research on structured linear recurrent architectures that balance expressivity, efficiency, and scalability.

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